

Reduction of Benzophenone with Sodium Borohydride

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Introduction

This experiment aims to reduce benzophenone to diphenylmethanol (Benhydrol). Sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) is used as the reducing agent that converts aldehydes and ketones to alcohols. The experiment takes note of the reaction time by monitoring the starting materials amounts that remain at the end of the experiment. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) is used to monitor the reaction.

Balanced Chemical Equation

The Balanced Chemical equation for the reaction

Reaction Mechanism

Ketones such as benzophenone have polarized Carbon-Oxygen bonds, unsymmetrical charge distribution and unsaturation represented by $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond. These are key considerations when rationalizing ground state thermal reactions of such compounds. Most of the ketone reactions can be represented in terms of nucleophile initial attacks at the carbonyl groups' partially positively charged carbon atom. The attack by nucleophile produces an oxygen centered anion that abstract a proton in yielding the product observed. The reaction medium may have the proton source present in it or in can be availed in the workup procedure.

One of the examples of reactions that can be represented in terms of nucleophilic attack is the ketones' reaction with metal hydride reagents. The benzophenone reaction using sodium borohydride results in benzhydrol, in the form of diphenylmethanol.

Procedure (Reaction)

Dissolve the benzophenone (100mg) in ethanol in a 25 ml conical flask. Add a small magnetic stirrer bar and place the flask on the magnetic stirrer in order to stir the solution magnetically. In a small test-tube, dissolve the sodium borohydride (15 mg, 2) in cold water (1.5 ml) and add this solution on drop at a time, using a Pasteur pipette, to the stirred ethanolic solution of benzophenone at room temperature. After all the sodium borohydride has been added, continue to stir the mixture at room temperature.

(Monitoring the reaction)

After fifteen minute intervals carry out TLC analyses as follows. Using a Pasteur pipette to withdraw 5 drops of the reaction mixture and place it in small sample vial. Add 5 drops of 2M hydrochloric acid and 10 drops of ethyl acetate. Stopper the vial and shake it gently for a few moments. Carefully remove the stopper and let the contents of the vial settle. The vial should contain two layers, an aqueous layer at the bottom, and an ethyl acetate solution on top. Carefully remove some of the ethyl acetate extract using a glass capillary (make sure that none of the aqueous gets into the capillary) and spot onto a silica gel TLC plate.

Data and Observation

Mass of benzophenone used	0.1g
Moles of Benzophenone used	0.0005488
Molar Mass of Benzophenone	182.2gmol ⁻¹
Mass of NaBH ₄	0.015g
Molar Mass of NaBH ₄	37.83gmol ⁻¹
Molar Mass of diphenylmethanol	184.23 gmol ⁻¹
Meting point of diphenylmethanol	69°

Moles of benzophenone used

Moles= mass of benzophenone/moles of benzophenone

$$\text{Moles} = 0.1\text{g}/182.2\text{ gmol}^{-1}$$

$$\text{Moles} = 0.0005$$

Moles of NaBH₄ used. NaBH₄ is the source of hydride ions. Calculation of the number of hydride ions used.

Moles of Sodium borohydride= mass of Sodium borohydride/molecular weight of NaBH₄

$$\text{Moles} = 0.015\text{g}/37.83\text{ gmol}^{-1}$$

$$\text{Moles} = 0.0004$$

There are four hydride ions in every molecule of sodium borohydride

$$0.0004\text{ moles} \times 4$$

$$= 0.0016\text{ moles}$$

Limiting reagent

The Balanced Chemical equation for the reaction

Results

The equation indicates that the ratio between the moles of benzophenone and sodium borohydride is 4:1.

Therefore, 0.0005 moles of benzophenone would need 0.00013 moles of sodium borohydride, but there were 0.0004 in the solution. This implies that sodium borohydride was in excess, and therefore, benzophenone was the limiting agent.

Likewise, 0.0004 moles of sodium borohydride would need 0.0016 moles of benzophenone, but only 0.0005 moles was in the solution. This also means that benzophenone was the limiting reagent.

The theoretical yield of diphenylmethanol in grams

The theoretical yield is calculated using moles of the limiting reagent. Therefore,

Grams- Moles x Molar Mass

Theoretical yield of diphenylmethanol= moles of benzophenone x molar mass of diphenylmethanol

Theoretical yield= 0.0005 x 184.238

Theoretical Yield=0.0921g

The actual percentage yield of the reaction

The percentage yield of diphenylmethanol is calculated by dividing the actual yield of the diphenylmethanol by the theoretical yield of diphenylmethanol and multiplying by 100/1

$$\text{Actual \% yield} = 0.065\text{g}/0.0921\text{g} \times 100 = 70.58\%$$

The percentage yield is lower than 100% because there could be impurities in either substance leading to impurities in the product. Another reason is that there could be apparatus errors such as not using a wash bottle to wash all of the substances into the solution and left some solute on the side of the flask or beaker. Another reason is that there might not have been complete reaction due to imperfect conditions. Some of the reacting particles may not have acquired the energy required to collide and resulted in the formation of products.

Key IR and NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry data for diphenylmethanol

IR Spectroscopy

Frequency	Assignment
3200-3600	<input type="checkbox"/> (OH, alcohol)
3027-3086	<input type="checkbox"/> (CH, sp ²)
2900	<input type="checkbox"/> (CH, sp ³)
1495, 1598	<input type="checkbox"/> (C=C, aromatic)
1458	<input type="checkbox"/> (CH, bend)
1032	<input type="checkbox"/> (C-OH, alcohol)
702, 735	oop, mono-subst. arene

Discussion

The experiment takes note of the time used for the reaction. The duration of the reaction is done by monitoring the starting materials amounts that remain in the reaction using a thin layer chromatography. The reaction is complete when there is no starting materials remain and working up should be done. Reaction monitoring using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) is done by directly spotting tiny reaction mixture amounts onto the TLC plates (Epple and Ebbinghaus, 1967). The spotting is done at regular intervals and checking how much starting materials remain by running the plates using Hydrochloric Acid. Small samples are withdrawn and each sample is worked up instead. The working up is equally done to the final reaction mixture to end up with the product. The organic compounds solutions are obtained and analyzed by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). The product isolation is achieved through filtration after doing a work up. The product is then crystallized to purify. Millimolar scales are used in the reaction, which require special care to avoid or minimize mechanical losses, which can be substantial. Weighing is done using analytical balances.

Conclusion

This experiment reduces the aromatic benzophenone to diphenylmethanol (Benhydrol). Sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) is used as the reducing agent. It is a mild reducing agent that converts aldehydes and ketones to alcohols. Reactions involving Sodium borohydride are carried out in isopropanol, methanol or ethanol to speed up the reaction and shorten the completion time. The reducing agent is used in excess to ensure that the carbonyl group is completely reduced.

Sodium borohydride is fairly soluble in organic solvents. For this reason, the reaction is carried out in an aqueous ethanolic solution.

References

Epple, M., & Ebbinghaus, S. (1998). Reduction of solid benzophenones with sodium borohydride. *Journal of thermal analysis and calorimetry*, 52(1), 165-176.